

THE HISTORY OF BOOK PUBLISHING AND THE ART OF READING**Murotova Yulduz Fakhriddin kizi**

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Abstract. This scientific article covers a number of issues, such as researching the history of bibliography and determining its role as a means of reflecting reality in a time when changes are observed in the attitude of the digital technological society to information and books. In the history of literature, the opinions of leading scientists and experts on publishing work and the concept of books are presented, and the extent to which the development of the history of literature has been researched in the national publishing system is analyzed from a scientific point of view.

Keywords: book, publishing, bibliopolitics, reading studies, xylography, printing.

INTRODUCTION

The history of books and publishing is an integral part of human development. Publishing, as the main element of presenting ideas and opinions, can touch almost all spheres of human activity. In all aspects of the development of society and the state, from politics to the economy and the education system, it continues to develop and shine through publishing products.

Literary history is an important part of the publishing industry. According to a number of researchers, the history of bibliography is an independent scientific field of the publishing process. Another group of researchers emphasizes that the historical content includes all the basics of the publishing industry: editing, bibliopolitics and reading studies, etc [2].

MAIN PART

According to the concept of Russian bibliographer, Doctor of History Sergey Luppov, the history of bibliography includes:

- creating a book (organizational issues related to the technical and general issues of the publishing process, copying the book manuscript, the subject of printed and handwritten books, censorship, fonts, signature, spelling, decorating the book);
- book distribution (book sales and other methods of its distribution, influence of foreign book products, book exchange);
- formation of large book funds and libraries (conditions of their creation, composition, impact on the development of society);
- book use (characteristics of the demands of readers, students of different strata, the book as an active way of manifesting these demands).

In accordance with these stages, the field of publishing includes a number of special disciplines consisting of a complete system of knowledge that differs in its subject and object:

- publishing knowledge system;
- book trade knowledge system (bibliopolistics);
- library knowledge system (librarianship);
- bibliographic knowledge system (bibliographic science).

Doctor of History, Professor Yevgeny Nemirovsky suggested that the definition of the concept of "History of Books" should be based on the following correspondences: the category "form of social consciousness - literature - book" corresponds to the category "content - work - document". It follows that "the history of forms of social consciousness is connected with the development of content, the history of literature is connected with the evolution of works, and the history of books is connected with the evolution of documents" [4].

Analyzing scientific research, we can see that the history of publishing covers several centuries. If its origin is described in the testimonies and memories of Johannes Gutenberg, the inventor of the printing press, and his contemporaries, we

can see that the history of bibliography is directly related to ancient times. Thus, we divide the history of literature into 4 periods:

- The era of manuscript books;
- The period of invention and establishment of book printing;
- Industrial printing era;
- Modern (informed) era.

The era of manuscript books developed in Ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, Ancient Greece, India, Arab countries, Turkestan and a number of other countries. the foundation stone was laid for the civilization of his activity.

The method of reproduction of manuscripts was discovered long ago. That is, it was a molding method. It was popular in ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia. In particular, the Sumerians (3rd millennium BC) used molds carved on boards, while the Egyptians used molds carved on baked clay.

In Central Asia, book culture and the publishing industry have a unique, rich tradition and centuries-old history. We can see the history of Uzbekistan's literature in the researches of a number of well-known scientists. Yevgeniy Betger (1887-1956), a famous historian and orientalist, a well-known book scholar of Central Asia, was one of the first to make a significant contribution to the study of book publishing. His research "From the history of book publishing in Uzbekistan (on the 70th anniversary of the first Uzbek lithographic book)"[xiii] was, in fact, the first scientific work devoted to the beginning of book printing in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan. The issues considered in the work are related to: the emergence of book printing, the first printing presses and the emergence of lithographs, it shows information about the time of publication of the first printed books in Uzbek and Russian languages [5].

After Turkistan was annexed to the Russian Empire in the middle of the 19th century, a small printing house was brought to Tashkent, which started working under the control of the military district headquarters in 1868 and served the needs of the Russian administration. The following year, a second printing house was

opened in Tashkent for the publication of the official newspaper "Turkestanskije vedomosti", which is considered the first periodical in East Asia. The newspaper "Turkestanskije vedomosti" operated from 1870 to 1917. In addition to the Cyrillic alphabet, the Arabic alphabet was also used in the printing press, and it was used to print the supplements to "Turkestanskije vedomosti" in Uzbek and Kazakh ("Türkistan Uəlayatı Gazetı") [4].

CONCLUSION

One of the important and urgent issues facing us now is to provide research and scientific solutions in the field in order to ensure the quality of electronic publications as well as paper publications in accordance with the requirements of the times. In this place, it consists of developing a national publishing system and applying it to the field, taking into account the issues of book editing, its design and marketing. In the next chapter, the results of the research of the world's most advanced and experienced publishers in this regard and the scientific proposals given to it will be discussed.

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